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The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) wishes to thank all the reviewers for their intellectual contributions by timely reviewing manuscripts, and supporting the journal's vision of "*Enriching Beautiful Minds towards Intelligent Minds*".

From the desk of the Editor-in-Chief, the Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) would like to thank all the reviewers who made it possible to publish this volume, Volume 7, Issue 1, May 2023.

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TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

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